

Information Systems: A critical review

Author: **Eltigani Musa**

Executive Summary

The 21st century presented a revolutionary era in technology. Among one of the most important advances is information systems (IS). Although the concept was developed in the late 20th century, researchers have struggled to achieve consensus over definitions of IS due to their wide application. They have been an imperative part of the digital transformation as businesses shift from conventional methods to more elaborate methods of handling their operations. Moreover, organizations have embraced big data analytics and decision support systems (DSS) to achieve competitive advantage. However, the challenge of harmonising automation and accountability in decision support systems still exists. It is evident that the processes of incorporating moral considerations in DSS are still a long way from achieving complete autonomy.

1. Introduction

The progressive nature of technological sophistication in the global environment has been a primary strength of many sectors of the world. More specifically, the use of computers over the last few decades has resulted in massive changes in productivity, profitability, and business communications. This paper offers an integrated summary of five scholarly sources by different authors regarding information technology. These include four scholarly articles that include journals and whitepapers, as well as a webinar. The paper will infuse the different concepts put forward by the authors to offer a comprehensive understanding of the issue of information systems in the 21st century.

2. Information Systems (IS)

- **Towards a proper definition of IS**

In most of the papers, the authors have come up with individual perspectives on information systems. Checkland (1988) argued that information systems (IS) was a broad field that could not be interpreted using vague language. In particular, the author blamed Wiener and Fischer – the pioneers of the theory of information systems, for their weak groundwork in the establishment of IS's operating frameworks (Checkland, 1988). Checkland further faults the founders for their synonymous understanding of the terms 'signal' and 'information' while they are significantly two distinct items.

In this regard, Checkland (1988) applied an interpretive approach with the assumption that various understandings of the term 'information systems' were constructed socially through semantics, documents and common meanings. As one of the classical researchers in the field of IS, Checkland's definition of IS systems integrates the concepts of systems thinking, information systems, information theories and ideas (Checkland, 1988). In his theory, Checkland asserts that the definition lacked to assimilate the tenets of systems thinking, a critical addition to theoretical and practical concerns.

Checkland embarks on proving the hypothesis that the field of IS lacks the clarity necessary to scrutinise the discipline at its fundamentals with the intention of maturing an approach that could deliver practical and theoretical aid as well as establish the basis for prospective work in the field. The author's hypothesis was valid. By then (1988), the field of computer technologies was still at its developmental stages. The author was one of the scientists who foresaw the potential held by information systems in the coming decades. In Checkland's studies, he concluded that some of the concepts left out in the definition of IS had to be incorporated in the general understanding of IS. He attributed the failure of several systems established in the 70s and 80s of the 20th century to weak groundwork on principles of informational theory (Checkland, 1988).

On the other hand, Paul (2007) focused on the problematic understanding of the issue of information systems in the public. He utilizes a conventional approach in researching the problem. The author cites that the general society lacks an understanding of IS; this often

leads to further complications in distinguishing information technology and computer science. Additionally, the author asserts that if not addressed, the issue would burgeon and become a thorn in the future generations' understanding of various computational concepts. Therefore, the works of Checkland and Paul are interrelated in the sense that they are aimed at ironing out inconsistencies present in the field of information systems.

Paul (2007) adopted a contemporary approach in debating the challenges of information systems. Unlike Checkland (1988), the author presented his studies in an era where many organisations were incorporating information systems in their operations. However, the author cited five main challenges to information systems; asserting that they had to be eliminated for the field to flourish. First, the author cites that IS never really got out of the tech circle. For the public, it represented a technology with more of negatives than positives. In responding to this challenge, the author suggests better interpretation of the relationship between software and technology. Secondly, the author attributes that many students have steered off course related to computing and IT. This affects the quantity of talent available to propel the field. Third, the author identified that researchers in the field have lacked the quality material for publication in IS scholarly articles. This lack of optimism in the field presented a barrier in the advancement of the field of IS as a significant pillar in the 21st century digital society. Fourth, the numerous reviews and revisions of works in top journals have hampered the publication of content in journals. Finally, there has not been a consensus on the definitions of information systems (Paul, 2007).

The last point mentioned above creates the main link between Checkland's (1988) and Paul's (2007) literature. Almost two decades later, Paul (2007) experiences the same dilemma that Checkland had earlier pointed out. However, Paul (2007) offers the explanation that the broad nature of IS has yielded definitions from multiple factions. Nevertheless, these amorphous definitions have spiralled the field into further discord.

The author proceeds to offer a more plausible mechanism towards arriving at a conclusive definition for IS systems to shed light on how it should be perceived. To begin

with, the author suggests an elimination of the definitions of IS as an extension of closely related fields such as Information Technology and Computer Science. These have proven to have a detrimental effect; they shadow the development of information systems as an independent field. Albeit this would take a reasonable amount of time, the intervention of global entities such as the Conference of IS Professors in the United Kingdom would provide ease in the process. Secondly, the author encourages the use of informal processes to ensure proper work for IT users.

Checkland and Paul, using different approaches, highlight the nature of IS systems. It is imperative to note that both acknowledged IS as a flourishing field given the exponential routes of expansion it created before them. Although Checkland's work can be considered as more classical, his views and assertions have been incorporated into a advancing the theories of information systems. Among one of his most important observations is that there existed the need to advance factors that characterise the information system environment. Applications of this form of thinking are present in other academic literature. Although not directly quoted, Oracle limited reveals that creation of revolutionary data collection, analysis, and distribution mechanisms is based on a proper understanding of the operating milieu (Oracle®, 2013). On the other hand, Paul (2007) suggests the development of a revolutionary head-on approach to the challenges of information systems. Given their adaptability, there is the necessity for achieving headway in the interpretation of information systems, information technology and computer science without any of them exerting hegemony over the other. They should be viewed as compliments to each other, rather than one being secondary to the other.

- **The Effects of Information Systems and the Digital Transformation**

While the two authors above concentrated on the issue of the ambiguity in the definition of information systems, others went in-depth in decoding the nature of information systems and its effects in the modern society. In a webinar titled “A holistic Approach to Digital Transformation,” various speakers discussed about the digital disruption

attributed to technological advancement. One of the most affected areas is the business sector. Businesses have turned to information systems in order to boost their operational excellence. This move has been labelled as ‘digital transformation’.

Digital disruption is primarily attributed to the advancements in computer technology and information systems (AIIM International, 2016). In this phenomenon, businesses have steered away from traditional modes of operations and incorporated sophisticated methods that have resulted to increases in efficiency in operations. Although the move may have been interpreted as a blessing, others have viewed it as a curse. A proper incorporation of technologies, especially information systems, into daily operational frameworks will see massive improvements. However, unprofessional integration into organizational processes is a risky approach that may result in complete paralysis (Oracle®, 2013).

In the webinar, Connie Moore – an experienced researcher in digital technologies, states that many facilities often have the fear of getting it wrong. This is also a key challenge labelled by Oracle Systems, a leading designer of information technology systems, software systems, and information management technologies. In a Whitepaper by the company in 2013, the company supported the concept of information being a central competitive advantage for organizations. Moreover, it acknowledges the heterogeneity of information systems and their wide applications in contemporary organizations.

It is imperative to note that information systems are not the whole solution to challenges of modern businesses. They complement and catalyse effective operation; organisations still have to rely on other components. For instance, in the business context, digital transformation must be accompanied by the development of efficient business models, renewed perspectives towards innovation, incorporation of technology in all organizational levels and boosting customer experiences. Moore (2016) asserts that transformation must be accompanied by achieving harmony between inside and outside processes within businesses. This involves characterizing the requirements of the

organization and its clientele in order to develop seamless interaction pathways that maximize interactions and constructive discourses to enhance business relationships.

Checkland (1988) and Paul (2007) arguments can be applied to get a better grip on the concept of digital transformation. Moore (AIIM – 2016) asserts a system of seamless communication between all parties within an organisation. Indirectly, this calls for a uniform understanding of the role of information systems within and outside organisations to facilitate seamless interactions between all parties. As Paul (2007) suggests, there is the need to achieve unanimity in the perception towards IS in order to nurture the general confidence of organizations in the field. This is a significant observation that has to be taken into consideration since 80 % of traditional business types will be eliminated by 2020 using information systems (Khan, in AIIM, 2016).

Information systems in the digital transformation are have been known to have several inherent advantages over their traditional counterparts. Briefly, conventional approaches applied intricate methodologies that hindered organisational growth. Modern systems are engineered to eliminate this form of complexity; therefore, they position businesses in better positions to expand, become flexible, and enhance decision-making processes. They mitigate the dependence of businesses on ad-hoc methodologies and foster cooperation between departments.

3. Information Management and Big Data

The 21st century, also referred to as the digital age, has seen the evolution of myriad technologies. Although there are myriad inventions and innovations, only a few have managed to achieve commercial success. Khan (AIIM, 2016) highlights that in order to achieve informational excellence; ‘organizations must move and integrate data, business processes, analytics and proper management as well as storage’. This points out to the theory and practice of information management. According to Oracle, businesses have recognized the importance of data in achieving competitive advantage. This has been boosted by the progression in the fields of data collection, organization, storage, and

analytics. However, the amount of data collected has increased to very large volumes thereby posing challenges to its management and optimal use.

Currently, the use of data in managing organisations has become a necessity, especially in large establishments. They have spent numerous resources in improving data handling capabilities in their respective operations (Oracle®, 2013). The large data sizes known as ‘Big Data’ have generated discord among researchers in their definitions and applications. However, the most basic definition is that its volume is very big. It presents a similar challenge to that of defining information systems.

Big Data, just like information systems, has often been associated with the fields of information technology and computer science. Consequently, this has attributed to its slow recognition in the 21st century despite its roots in the late 20th century. However, scientists have generally agreed on the fact that ‘not all large volumes of data are big data’. In this assertion, the four dimensions of big data were established. The first of these is volume. It has no definite value and it is relative to the size of the industry applying it. The second is velocity; for data to be categorised as ‘Big data’, it has to be generated in real time (Oracle®, 2013). This implies effective and operational data collection, organization, storage, and analytics to avoid delays that may hamper the information management process (AIIM International, 2016). The third ‘v’ represents variety. It refers to the language and syntax of the data sets in order to generate important links for information systems. As explained by Moore (AIIM, 2016), operational excellence must rely on proper integration of data and processes among other variables. Therefore, must make rational decisions regarding vital elements in organisational operations. Finally, the final ‘v’ refers to value. The data must be commercially viable whether in raw or processed form.

Most advances in technology are geared towards profit maximization. Business organizations are the bulk of the customers for information systems and related technologies. According to a paper by Cummings (2006), contemporary businesses have continuously aimed at achieving complete automation in their activities. The author

further asserts that ‘technology has become an ingrained part of most organisations’ as they endeavour to achieve their strategic objectives and subsequently obtain advantage over others. For this reason, information systems have become common tools utilized in making strategic, financial, and operational decisions (Cummings, 2006). Of these three decisions, the most important are strategic decisions.

The term strategic emanates from the word ‘strategy’ that defines a long-term tactic or course of action. In this case, strategic decisions in organisations aimed at improving the organisation’s long-term future. Strategic systems (IS for strategic decisions) are composed four elements (Oracle®, 2013). These include decision support systems – used to align administrative choices with organizational objectives; database systems (DS) – used to collect or ‘mine’ data from organizational activities; enterprise resource planning (ERP) systems – used to incorporate business operations for the maximum performance of a business and the real time information system – utilized in monitoring business operations for timely reaction to quality indicators.

Decision support systems (DSS) are some of the most applied technologies by organisations. The word ‘organisations’ is not limited to establishments with a profit motive. It is meant to incorporate all types of systems ranging from government owned to private owned. Initially, they were established to support military decisions but were later integrated into business application as time progressed (Cummings, 2006). Organisations applying the use of DSS in their administrative activities are acknowledged to be in better positions than others are in the same environment (Oracle®, 2013). Evidences of top performing companies, such as McDonalds, that have achieved acclaimed success global business, support this. However, DSS are not devoid of challenges.

4. Automation and Accountability in Decision Support Systems (DSS)

It was earlier mentioned Decision Support Systems (DSS) contribute to the effectiveness and efficiency of operational decisions. However, can they be fully automated? Cummings (2006) highlights the various advantages of IS systems that have increased

reliance from organizations. Despite all the advantages, DSS designers are faced with the challenge of harmonizing the elements of automation and accountability in decision support systems.

DSS designers are constantly working towards the elimination of the human element in information systems. They are aiming at assimilating the element of simplicity in their operations to remove the barrier of complexity in decision-making. This is a challenge since the process of decision-making involves selection from a range of alternatives that include legal and ethical considerations collected from data of various businesses. This brings back the statement by Oracle that decision support systems analyse databases in order to gather trends and insights on patterns (Oracle®, 2013). While this may be easy for rigid legal considerations, it is often generates complexities in terms of ethical considerations.

The ethical consideration is regarded as the moral accountability of an organization's actions towards the society. According to Cummings (2006), researchers have struggled to maintain a balance between accountability and automation. Although automation simplifies organisational processes, it complicates some decisions that may have ethical considerations. This occurs because creating a database for ethical considerations of actions is a huge challenge. Often, there is a huge variation in moral and ethical beliefs across populations. Consequently, incorporating these variables would lead to a complex DSS that would not yield the desired result.

On the other hand, automation relies on the principle of simplicity. The analysis of data by information systems should be fast to enhance the delivery of results (Oracle®, 2013). It focuses on saving time and resources. In making a DSS complex, then operational costs would render the system inadequate. Cummings (2006) asserts that automation often has the disadvantages of making systems rigid and brittle. Therefore, they may lower the quality of decision making in organisational workforces. In this respect, the author proposes the creation of a moral buffer that allows the human element to distance itself

from an immoral action. This can be done through a computer interface or item. Through transfer of moral agency, the ethical partiality burden is shifted from the human being (Cummings, 2006).

Although the idea of shifting moral agency seems appealing, it is subjective to various situations. To begin with, it is only suitable in closed loop decisions – these are decisions that are predefined and have very low probability of deviation. Secondly, they are not suitable for situations that deal with human lives. Interface designers should be aware of responsibility factors and create effective moral buffers that lift the burden of excessive cognitive strain in the process of employees making decisions in the duties. However, they should have well-defined ethical considerations (Cummings, 2006).

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, the dynamics of technology have never ceased to be intriguing. It is strange to see discourses established decades earlier persist into the modern generation. In this regard, there is the need to establish robust mechanisms that promote the independent development of the fields of information systems and Big Data. After ascertaining their independence, organisations should adopt the use of these technologies and make use of the opportunities. The paper has not failed to mention about the designers of information systems. They should incorporate morals in creating decision support systems and respect the ethical boundaries stipulated by the society. Overall, the society should be braced for any changes in the field of technology.

References

AIIM International, 2016. *[Webinar Replay] A Holistic Approach to Digital Transformation*. [Online]
Available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qrBank4FDzo>
[Accessed 14 June 2016].

Checkland, P., 1988. Information systems and systems thinking: time to unite?. *International Journal of Information Management*, Volume 8, pp. 239-248..

Cummings, M., 2006. *Automation and Accountability in Decision Support System Interface Design*, Boston: Massachusetts Institute of Technology.

Oracle®, 2013. *Information Management and Big Data: A Reference Architecture*. New York: Oracle.

Paul, R. J., 2007. Challenges to information systems: time to change. *European Journal of Information Systems*, Volume 16, p. 193–195.